

Organization of knowledge ecosystems: Prefigurative and partial forms

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ABSTRACT

This paper provides a unique perspective on knowledge ecosystems by studying their organization. Grounded in empirical evidence, we propose that knowledge ecosystems consist of users and producers of knowledge that are organized around a joint knowledge search. A distinction is drawn between knowledge ecosystems searching for a knowledge domain and those searching *within* an identified knowledge domain, respectively characterized as prefigurative and partial forms of organizing. In a knowledge ecosystem organized in prefigurative form (to identify a knowledge domain), actors whose participation is affiliated, self-resourced, and unobliged probe that domain to identify and establish shared knowledge as a basis for collective actorhood, with no formal rules or coordination mechanisms. In a knowledge ecosystem organized in partial form (where a knowledge domain has already been identified), actors search and reveal problem- and solution-related knowledge, participating though formal membership and access to resources, and their contributions are monitored. The present study contributes to the literature by 1) specifying the distinct types of joint search performed by knowledge ecosystems; 2) considering how the nature of joint search affects how knowledge ecosystems are organized; and 3) distinguishing two forms of organizing knowledge ecosystems, with a focus on participation and coordination.

1. Introduction

Large-scale scientific and societal problems tend to be extremely complex, have multiple causes, and will never have one perfect solution. As the required expertise to address such complex problems is both specialized and scattered, the search for solutions and related knowledge creation increasingly occurs in ecosystems of individual and organizational actors, involving diverse inputs, resource commitments, and motives. This potential has led national policy makers in many countries to actively promote knowledge and innovation ecosystems as engines for growth and well-being. For example, within the Finnish innovation policy, Strategic Centers for Science, Technology, and Innovation were established, operating between the public and private sectors, with the aim to pursue and implement dynamic industry-driven research programs (e.g. Halme et al., 2014). However, recent experiences have confirmed the challenges of sustaining collaboration among actors in such initiatives (Sinnewe et al., 2016). For that reason, it is important for both policy and practice to understand how actions are coordinated in knowledge ecosystems, and how the requisite resources are deployed.

The present study focuses on these emerging collectives – *knowledge ecosystems* – in which actors such as universities, public research institutions, and for-profit firms collaborate to create new knowledge in a

pre-competitive setting (van der Borgh et al., 2012; Clarysse et al., 2014; Valkokari, 2015). Knowledge ecosystems may form around specific technological or societal challenges (Dougherty and Dunne, 2011) or among geographically co-located organizations in complementary fields (van der Borgh et al., 2012). Knowledge ecosystems may also be purposefully facilitated to address a set of basic or applied science problems, leading over time to knowledge exploitation and actor-specific appropriation (Franzoni and Sauerermann, 2014; Perkmann and Schildt, 2015). Such ecosystems accommodate complementarities in value creation (Clarysse et al., 2014), resulting in more effective search for new knowledge than by any individual actor alone. At a theoretical level, several important areas on knowledge ecosystems remain unexplored—in particular, the domain of knowledge creation and search, the nature of participation in knowledge creation and search, and the coordination of activities supporting knowledge creation and search.

The present study is motivated by these practical and theoretical implications of the *organizational* aspects in knowledge ecosystems. Here, the term *organization* broadly refers to any “multiagent system with identifiable boundaries and a system-level goal toward which the constituent actor’s efforts are expected to contribute” (Puranam et al., 2014: 163). In the same way as individual firms, a knowledge ecosystem can be viewed as a form of organizing. However, as Wilhoit and Kisselburgh (2015) put it, “... when we move away from the *terra firma*

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of corporations, nonprofits, and social organizations, we find ourselves on shaky ground in determining what is and is not an organization” (p. 573). While the absence of hierarchies and related coordination mechanisms suggests that knowledge ecosystems are in some sense less organizable than firms, they nevertheless meet the conditions of patterning and structure that create a minimum viable context for organization (see Schreyögg and Sydow, 2010). On that basis, we argue for the theoretical need to examine knowledge ecosystems as forms of organization and organizing. In so doing, we also hope to contribute to existing research on network (Powell et al., 1996) and ecosystem structure (Clarysse et al., 2014; Still et al., 2014); governance of joint knowledge search (Felin and Zenger, 2014; Bogers et al., 2016; Järvenpää and Välikangas, 2016); and, more broadly, the coordination of knowledge and innovation ecosystems, which to date has focused mainly on the role of focal firm (e.g., Rohrbeck et al., 2009; Leten et al., 2013; Ritala et al., 2013). To those ends, the study addresses the following research question: *How are knowledge ecosystems organized? Specifically, we focus on: What is the nature of the knowledge search in knowledge ecosystems? Who participates in knowledge search? How are knowledge search and knowledge creation activities coordinated?*

This approach is informed by recent suggestions (e.g., Gawer, 2014) that an organizational perspective can further our understanding of knowledge creation in knowledge ecosystems. We believe the present study is the first to integrate two previously separate streams of research on knowledge ecosystems (early-stage, pre-competitive, and problem-based knowledge creation and search) (Nickerson and Zenger, 2004; van der Borgh et al., 2012; Clarysse et al., 2014; Felin and Zenger, 2014; Valkokari, 2015) and organizational activities outside and beyond the formal organization (e.g., Ahrne and Brunsson, 2011; Gulati et al., 2012). To address the above research questions, we conducted a collective qualitative case study which assembled rich empirical evidence from seven knowledge ecosystems organized around solving challenging problems and involving diverse actors from industry and academia.

Our findings contribute to the knowledge ecosystems literature in a number of respects. First, we show how knowledge ecosystems are organized around multi-actor knowledge creation and search. On that basis, we propose a refined, empirically grounded definition of the knowledge ecosystem: *A knowledge ecosystem consists of users and producers of knowledge, organized around joint knowledge search.* Second, on the basis of our empirical study, we contend that knowledge ecosystems differ in terms of the nature and target of joint knowledge search. The findings differentiate knowledge ecosystems searching *for* a knowledge domain from those searching *within* an identified knowledge domain. We propose that while the search *for* a knowledge domain involves probing and formulating a common goal, search *within* a knowledge domain involves selectively revealing and reinforcing the common goal. Third, we demonstrate that the nature of joint search has implications for how knowledge ecosystems are organized, and we distinguish between two forms of organizing: *prefigurative* and *partial*. Finally, we discuss how these forms enable the organization of participation and coordination. Together, these contributions enhance our understanding of how knowledge ecosystems search for and create new knowledge, and how they are organized around these tasks.

2. Conceptual background

Innovation activities have become increasingly interconnected and open, involving more heterogeneous groups of actors and inputs than before (Samarra and Biggiero, 2008; Corsaro et al., 2012). This phenomenon is reflected in the broad literature on open innovation (e.g., Dahlander and Gann, 2010; West et al., 2014), where the *innovation ecosystem* lens is increasingly used to understand the growing interdependence and scope of systemic and networked innovation (e.g., Rohrbeck et al., 2009; West et al., 2014). Innovation ecosystems are seen to enable both creation and capture of value from novel, complex

value propositions (Dattée et al., 2018) and are typically organized around a focal firm, technology, platform or value proposition (Ritala et al., 2013; Autio and Thomas, 2014). While related to these literatures, the scope of the present study is much narrower, examining ecosystems in the very early phases of innovation—initial knowledge creation and search. In contrast to the *knowledge ecosystems* that focus on early stages of knowledge creation (Clarysse et al., 2014), innovation ecosystems encompass the broader scope of exploration and exploitation, or the process of invention-to-commercialization (see e.g., Valkokari, 2015; Dattée et al., 2018).

For innovation ecosystems and knowledge ecosystems alike, the key challenge is how such loose collectives can be organized to achieve uncertain, complex, and often highly ambitious goals. To ground this question for the purposes of empirical investigation, the next section brings together two distinct research streams, merging insights from the knowledge ecosystems literature with the literature on organization above and beyond organizations.

2.1. Knowledge ecosystems and their organizing requirements

As knowledge ecosystems occur in pre-competitive, pre-commercialization settings, they are far removed from downstream activities that seek to exploit and commercialize newly generated knowledge (Valkokari, 2015). Knowledge ecosystems have been characterized as geographically co-located hotspots, in which local universities and public research organizations are typically the central actors (Clarysse et al., 2014), and where the key activity of knowledge exploration is accomplished through collaborative research work (Valkokari, 2015). Building on these conceptualizations, we view collaborative exploration of new knowledge as the central activity and output of knowledge ecosystems. However, we make two distinctions to the underlying assumptions. First, while co-location may play a role in knowledge creation, the capacity of new technologies to coordinate knowledge creation across considerable geographical distances means that this is no longer a determining factor in the existence of a knowledge ecosystem (see for example Still et al., 2014). Second, while universities and public research institutions play a key role in knowledge ecosystems, for-profit actors may also make significant inputs to knowledge exploration (see van der Borgh et al., 2012). On that basis, knowledge ecosystems can be seen as organizations comprising diverse actors bound together by a joint search for valuable knowledge while having independent agency also beyond the knowledge ecosystem. We believe that this conceptual lens facilitates examination of the organizing features of knowledge ecosystems, which will now be discussed in greater detail.

In general, any multi-partner collaboration for knowledge creation requires some level of joint goal setting and collective action toward that goal. In the first place, this requires a change in “the situation from one in which appropriators act independently to one in which they adopt coordinated strategies to obtain higher joint benefits” (Ostrom, 1990: 39). For knowledge ecosystems, this means that actors—whose interests may initially be independent and distinct—must engage in a *joint search* for new knowledge in pursuit of the higher-order goals that are unattainable through independent agency. This entails a deliberate search process for new and valuable knowledge that begins by searching and identifying problems – for example in the form of a common knowledge exploration goal – within which a search for high-value solutions is conducted (see Gavetti and Levinthal, 2000; Nickerson and Zenger, 2004; Macher, 2006; Felin and Zenger, 2014; Lopez-Vega et al., 2016). The search for problems is important because, once identified, these are broadly perceived as domains entailing the landscape of valuable opportunities, within which a solution search can be initiated (e.g., Nickerson and Zenger, 2004), although solutions can sometimes be found before problem identification (von Hippel and Von Krogh, 2015). In all cases, search performance depends on how actors’ participation is organized (Felin and Zenger, 2014).

Secondly, knowledge creation depends on the active *participation* of multiple actors. Participation in the knowledge ecosystem can vary in openness (e.g., Gulati et al., 2012), ranging from completely open (Franzoni and Sauermann, 2014) to more clearly bounded coalitions that focus, for example, on applied research around the specific needs of an individual actor (van der Borgh et al., 2012). However, not all actors in a knowledge ecosystem are equally active all the time (Davis and Eisenhardt, 2011) or simultaneously (Davis, 2016). Indeed, the ambiguity associated with newly formed research collaborations between multiple actors has been referred to as a “governance void” (Järvenpää and Välikangas, 2016). This means that the network of associations between actors is constantly evolving (Barry and Rerup, 2006), blurring the boundaries between the knowledge ecosystem and its environment, as well as between users and producers of knowledge (see for example Garud et al., 2008).

Third, the dispersion of knowledge and other resources across multiple entities (cf. Dougherty and Dunne, 2011) also requires *coordination* of knowledge creation across knowledge boundaries, domains of expertise (Bruns, 2013), and organizational boundaries (Rosenkopf et al., 2001). The literature on intra-organizational coordination suggests that boundary objects (Carlile, 2002, 2004), representations of work (Barley, 2015), and “trading zones” (Kellogg et al., 2006) help in communicating and navigating across knowledge boundaries. In the inter-organizational context, scholars have noted the presence of boundary organizations mediating, revealing, and enabling multiple goals (Perkmann and Schildt, 2015), open disclosure of intermediate inputs (Franzoni and Sauermann, 2014), as well as selective revealing of valuable knowledge (Alexy et al., 2013) as mechanisms that enable cross-boundary knowledge work.

The above characteristics broadly reflect the organizing requirements and challenges faced by knowledge ecosystems. Unlike traditional hierarchical organizations characterized by clearly specified boundaries, standardized processes of work, and centralized authority (Kellogg et al., 2006), the knowledge ecosystem’s organization has been described as fluid (Dobusch and Schoeneborn, 2015) and as an ongoing process (Barry and Rerup, 2006). Although goal abstractness and heterogeneity of participation and preference have inherent knowledge-generating properties (Garud et al., 2008; Wareham et al., 2014), it is often the case that, in knowledge ecosystems, “problems are ill-defined, preferences are fluid, and solutions emerge in action” (cf. Garud et al., 2008: 352). Dobusch and Schoeneborn (2015) suggested that while many contemporary forms of organizing do not entail strict boundaries or hierarchies as traditionally conceived, they are nevertheless organizable to some extent (see also King et al., 2010; Puranam et al., 2014). Indeed, Schreyögg and Sydow (2010) argued that a form of organization exists as soon as any patterning or linkage between actors emerges. While acknowledging that such organization may be fluid (Dobusch and Schoeneborn, 2015) and incomplete (Garud et al., 2008), it is important to note that knowledge ecosystems are not entirely self-organized, as there is always some meta-level intentional action (Valkokari, 2015). We will now discuss an emerging stream of literature on organizing beyond formal/traditional organizations, with which we adopt *sensitizing concepts* to our empirical analysis.

2.2. Understanding the organization of knowledge ecosystems: Sensitizing concepts

Before discussing the organization of knowledge ecosystems, it is important to address the fundamental question of what constitutes an organization. In the relevant literature, the different schools of thought include rational, natural, and open system perspectives (cf. Scott and Davis, 2007), any of which may be applied to a given organization. Here, our analytical approach is informed mainly by the natural systems perspective, in which organizations are defined as “collectives whose participants are pursuing multiple interests, both disparate and common, but who recognize the value of perpetuating the organization

as an important resource” (Scott and Davis, 2007: 30). This perspective aligns well with our goal of understanding the organizing of knowledge ecosystems. On that basis, the remainder of this section considers a number of definitions and perspectives that seem of immediate relevance.

Puranam et al. (2014) described an organization as a “multiagent system with identifiable boundaries and system-level goals toward which the constituent agent’s efforts are expected to contribute” (p. 163). They further suggest that any organization must solve four universal problems: task division and task allocation (jointly referred to as division of labor) and reward provision and information provision (jointly referred to as integration of effort). In similar fashion, March and Simon (1993) characterized organizations as “systems of coordinated action among individuals and groups whose preferences, information, interests or knowledge differ” (p. 2). For them, “organization theories describe the delicate conversion of conflict into cooperation, the mobilization of resources and the coordination of effort that facilitate the joint survival of an organization and its members” (p. 2).

As defined above, the concept of organization is not exclusively applicable to business firms or other “traditional” entities, and several emergent concepts facilitate description of organizations outside traditional forms. First, collective, inter-organizational action can be theoretically framed as a *meta-organization*, comprising legally autonomous individuals or organizations bound by a system-level goal (Gulati et al., 2012). In such meta-organizations, the incentives, motivations, and cognitions of actors may differ and are not linked by any formal authority such as the contractual framework of a traditional organization (Ahrne and Brunsson, 2005; Gulati et al., 2012). A second form of non-traditional organization is the *partial organization*. Juxtaposing the presence and absence of organizational elements, Ahrne and Brunsson (2011) distinguished between the partial organization and the complete, formal organization. While the latter includes all the elements of organizing—membership, hierarchy, monitoring, rules, and sanctions—the former “is based on only one or a few of these elements” (Ahrne and Brunsson, 2011). More recently, Dobusch and Schoeneborn (2015) coined the concept of *organizationality* to characterize a confluence of organizational identity and actorhood, in which the social collectives fulfill the minimum criteria of an organization: interconnectedness of decision-making, collective entity, and related identity (Ahrne and Brunsson, 2011; Dobusch and Schoeneborn, 2015). This concept further refines the earlier distinction between organization and non-organization by introducing “a more gradual differentiation” between those poles (Dobusch and Schoeneborn, 2015: 1006).

The above perspectives can help in explaining how knowledge ecosystems are organized. First, knowledge ecosystems of various kinds can be understood as meta-organizations (Ahrne and Brunsson, 2005; Gulati et al., 2012), in which autonomous individual and organizational actors come together in pursuit of the system-level goal of searching and creating knowledge. A meta-organization can enable collective agency (e.g., Sydow et al., 2012), incorporating institutional mechanisms that allow knowledge to be shared and created (e.g., Snow et al., 2011) while preserving the independence of individual actors. Second, the partial organizations perspective can help to explain how some knowledge ecosystems can be coordinated without possessing all the traditional organizing elements (cf. Ahrne and Brunsson, 2011). Indeed, while formal organizations can access a range of hierarchical mechanisms to search for problems and solutions, many R&D relationships afford an opportunity to explore and share knowledge more flexibly while preserving a high level of autonomy for the actors (see Felin and Zenger, 2014). Finally, the concept of organizationality serves to clarify how actorhood is created in knowledge ecosystems, even where actors are seen to have multiple different interests (cf. Scott and Davis, 2007: 30). Although remaining independent entities, actors who participate in knowledge ecosystems are expected to “organize” collectively, which requires relevant organizing elements.

Overall, we see these perspectives and concepts as highly valuable in providing further understanding of organizing loosely coupled ecosystems for knowledge search and creation. The following empirical part will utilize these as sensitizing concepts in this regard.

3. Methods

The following section discusses our methodological choices. After elaborating the research strategy and how it evolved, we explain our sampling strategy and describe the empirical setting of the study, explicating the logic of case selection. Finally, we discuss our approach to data collection and analysis.

3.1. Research strategy

This study had its origins in a broader research project on knowledge and innovation ecosystems. The organization of knowledge creation and knowledge work, and more generally knowledge ecosystems, was not of pre-defined theoretical interest; rather, that interest emerged during data collection and analysis for the larger research project, as a salient feature of the observed phenomenon and a promising theme for theoretical development. The study reported here, then, had no *a priori* research design or plan; instead, the design emerged iteratively and progressively, where the “researcher is well acquainted with the complexities of the problem before going to the field, but not too committed to a study plan” (Stake, 1981: 1) and “systematically reduces the breadth of their enquiry to give more concentrated attention to the emerging issues” (Parlett and Hamilton, 1972: 18). This progressive focusing is detailed here in order to remain truthful to the non-linearity and unpredictability of our research process (Sinkovics and Alfoldi, 2012).

To begin, we considered a multiple case study design (e.g., Eisenhardt, 1989) of seven cases, in which each research program would represent a case, so constituting its own unit of analysis. While conducting the within-case and cross-case analysis typical of a multiple case study, we noted the similarity in structure of the research programs (or the plan for a structure, where the program was still being prepared) in terms of stratification, roles, positions, and work packages (see Description of the Empirical Setting, below). However, we also observed the diversity of knowledge work and of approaches to participation and coordination, depending on whether the research program was still being prepared or whether collaborative research work had begun. For example, in the preparation phase, participants had yet to identify the goal and field of research and innovation; in contrast, already ongoing activities were conducted mainly within the identified field. This suggested that *what* is coordinated and *how* and *who* is participating differs according to whether the research program is in preparation or ongoing. On that basis, we formulated our overarching research question (*How are knowledge ecosystems organized?*) and redesigned the study as a collective case study (Stake, 1995) of two cases, with seven embedded units of analysis (see Fig. 1). The cases are instrumental (Stake, 1995), in that they facilitate our attempt to develop theory on organization of knowledge creation in knowledge ecosystems.

3.2. Sampling strategy

To address the research question, we purposefully sampled the research programs for the collective case study. The research programs were considered suitable for present purposes because although the actors were diverse and their goals heterogeneous, collaboration had to be coordinated if the collective was to accomplish its goal. Purposeful sampling seeks to select representative cases that vary “on the dimensions of theoretical interest” (Seawright and Gerring, 2008: 296). As our theoretical interest centered on the organization of knowledge ecosystems, we selected cases that exhibited differences of approach in this regard. We assumed that organization would vary according to whether

joint research and innovation activities remained to be identified or were already underway, as the respective complexities and challenges of knowledge creation would differ in nature and intensity. Succinctly capturing the reality of such research programs, Lindkvist (2005) noted that they “consist of people, most of whom have not met before, who have to engage in swift socialization and carry out a pre-specified task within set limits as to time and costs” (p. 1190). Moreover, the highly specialized competencies of participants can make it “difficult to establish shared understandings or a common knowledge base” (Lindkvist, 2005: 1190), and this is especially true of research programs under preparation.

The cases described here contrast identification of a joint research domain and research within a domain; the two overarching cases respectively include three and four research programs as embedded units. Both cases are instrumental—that is, their purpose is to support theoretical development, in this instance in relation to the organization of knowledge ecosystems. The research programs were “nested” within cases on the basis of our prior understanding, accumulated through the larger research project of which this study forms part, that participants sign a contract for collaboration before the research work begins. As this had not yet happened in three of these research programs, we felt confident in classifying them as identifying a joint research domain. In contrast, as a contract of collaboration had already been signed in the other four research programs, these could be characterized as conducting joint research in a domain.

3.3. Description of the empirical setting

The Strategic Centers for Science, Technology, and Innovation (SHOKs), established in 2006 by the Finnish government, provided the study’s empirical context. These centers were established principally to strengthen the competitiveness of Finland’s strategic industrial sectors, to improve their adaptive capability, and to create new national areas of expertise (Halme et al., 2014). The goal was to meet the innovation needs of Finnish industry and society within a five-to-ten-year period, and to “develop and apply new methods for cooperation, co-creation, and interaction” (Tekes, 2016). The SHOKs were administered by non-profit companies; operating between the public and private sectors, they pursued and implemented dynamic industry-driven research programs, as well as other development and innovation activities.

The SHOK research programs are built and operated by companies, research institutions, and universities of different sizes and sectors (i.e., information technology, health and wellbeing, energy, construction). As most research programs were administered by the IT industry SHOK, that sector is represented in each of the seven research programs that we studied. These programs focus on developing new knowledge in a pre-competitive setting through collaborative, jointly defined research activities, involving the recombination of existing knowledge and the creation of new knowledge and inventions to be applied in new products, technologies, and services. A research program typically has a lifespan of four years, which does not include time spent identifying the field of research and innovation activities, developing a research and innovation agenda, and commercializing the knowledge created. Funding agencies and companies finance the research program, and resources are allocated to universities and research institutions according to agreed program practices. Companies typically provide more than 50 per cent of this funding and lead the implementation of research (see also Järvenpää and Välikangas, 2016). Research institutes and universities complement and support the accomplishment of industry-driven research objectives. The output of the research program (new knowledge) is freely shared among the program members, which means that no member has proprietary rights to the intellectual property.

For each research program, there is a focus area director (representative of an industrial partner) and an academic coordinator (representative of a research partner); in some cases, there is also a

Fig. 1. Research design of the collective case study.

program coordinator. These individuals are mainly responsible for facilitation, conflict resolution, program-wide decision making, and enforcement of possible rules and sanctions. In addition, there may be work package leaders, depending on how the overarching goal of the program is decomposed into research themes and sub-tasks. In this sense, the internal division of labor varies across research programs, allowing the collective to dynamically organize how specified tasks are assigned to individual participants or groups. The participants themselves are responsible for managing their relationships within the collective, creating the necessary synergies, and facilitating collaboration within and/or across work packages. The administrative non-profit company plays a central role in preparation of the jointly defined research agenda, as they must bring all the relevant actors together in the first place and facilitate their early meetings. The role of the administrative non-profit company is subsequently more confined.

For present purposes, we conceptualized the research programs as *knowledge ecosystems*; within our case study research design, the research programs were *instrumental* (Stake, 1995) to our theoretical focus. The knowledge ecosystem concept was considered suitable as a conceptual lens for exploring this empirical phenomenon because of its emphasis on the interdependencies between participants. Within the chosen empirical setting, the participants were dependent on each other and needed to co-develop the necessary capabilities to accomplish the knowledge creation goal. At the same time, they remain independent as organizations, so embodying the key organizing challenges and features of knowledge ecosystems as we conceived of them. As the main interest and outcome of knowledge ecosystems is to generate new knowledge through joint research work and collaboration (see Clarysse et al., 2014; Valkokari, 2015), this seemed an appropriate characterization of our empirical setting. The pertinence of the ecosystem concept was further supported by our respondents' thoughts and reflections when asked about this issue.

Yes, ecosystem is a good word because I see that in many cases we are actually trying to solve really systemic problems. And in those cases, we might even create new kinds of ecosystems or at least fill the empty spaces in the existing ecosystem. (ReProG_Respondent A)

3.4. Data collection

The data collection process included semi-structured interviews and gathering of relevant archival material (Table 1). In addition, the first author had access to the intranet of one research program, where all the outputs of collaborative research work were documented. Although the intranet was not used as a data source, this access helped us to understand the nature of the joint research and innovation activities in greater detail.

The use of different data collection methods and the subsequent triangulation of data increased the trustworthiness of our research findings. We interviewed a total of twenty-seven key informants, utilizing archival material to identify those to be interviewed first. We then used the snowballing technique to identify further informants who could talk about the research program's activities and coordination. To ensure informants' suitability, the sample reflects the research programs' stratification or hierarchical levels; on that basis, we interviewed focus area directors, academic coordinators, program coordinators, work package leaders, and participants during the period Autumn 2014–Spring 2015. Four initial interviews provided a richer contextual understanding of the centers and research programs; these respondents are not included in Table 1. The remaining 23 respondents provided the study's main data,¹ representing the research programs' main actors; of the 23 interviewees, 13 represented companies (7 nonprofit and 6 for-profit), 4 represented public research organizations, and 6 represented universities.

Our interview guide consisted of three main sections. First, background questions of the respondent and his/her organization were asked. The second section of the interview guide focused on the preparation of the research program; the respondents were asked to describe what has happened in the program, who are its actors, and what type of activities are performed in the program preparation. Third, questions about the current state of the program were asked, focusing on the goals of the research program as well as on how activities are coordinated in the program. The interviews with those involved in ongoing research programs focused mainly on the third section of the interview guide, although some questions about the past were also asked. The interviews lasted between 35 and 85 min; fourteen were conducted in Finnish and thirteen in English. Interviews were tape-recorded and transcribed *verbatim* to facilitate systematic analysis of the raw data. The analytical procedure is explained in the next section.

3.5. Analysis

The analysis progressed from individual cases to cross-case analysis (Fig. 2). Analysis within and across cases was informed by the principles of grounded theory (see also Beyer and Hannah, 2002), given that framework's established analytic procedures for generating substantive theory (Strauss and Corbin, 1998; Charmaz, 2014), which were considered appropriate for the purposes of this study. Following Stake's (1995) collective case study approach, which falls within the constructivist paradigm (Baxter and Jack, 2008; Yazan, 2015), we adopted

¹ As two of our respondents were involved in two research programs, they appear twice in Table 1, explaining the listed total of 25 respondents.

Table 1
Data sources.

Cases and embedded units	Initial research and innovation objective(s)	Sectors involved	Number of partners at time of data collection	Year in lifecycle at time of data collection	Respondents	Additional sources of data
Joint research within a domain						
Research Program A	To create new ecosystems through the common basis and toolkit and by promoting innovation in the application and service layer, thus opening the IoT software development process.	Mainly information technology	50	Fourth and final year	2 - Focus Area Director, Academic Coordinator	Documentation of the research and innovation agenda, website
Research Program B	To boost Finnish international competitiveness through intelligent (context-sensitive, personalized, proactive) data processing technologies and services that add measurable value.	Mainly information technology	67	Third year	2 - Focus Area Director, Academic Coordinator	Documentation of the research and innovation agenda, website
Research Program C	To implement service enablers and new vertical services, based on existing and new enablers in currently underserved sectors.	Mainly information technology	85	Fourth and final year	4 - Focus Area Director, Academic Coordinator, Program Coordinator, Work Package Leader	Documentation of the research and innovation agenda, website
Research Program D	To create a foundation for the success of Finnish software-intensive businesses in the new digital economy.	Mainly information technology	40 (first year)	Second	2 - Focus Area Director, Academic Coordinator	Documentation of the research and innovation agenda, website
Identification of a joint research domain						
Research Program E	To establish cybersecurity as a key enabler for the development and maintenance of trust in the digital world.	Information technology	Unknown	Research program under preparation	2 - Focus Area Director, Responsible Leader	Documentation of the research and innovation agenda, website
Research Program F	To halve the time spent on treatment and institutional care, and to build successful value creation models to create business value from health; to create incentives for health service providers to make advances in health and wellbeing.	Health, information technology	Unknown	Research program under preparation	8 - Focus Area Director, Academic Coordinator, Work Package Leader, Responsible Leaders (2), Participants (3)	Documentation of the research and innovation agenda
Research Program G	To increase urban resilience and well-being, based on the socio-technical innovation of “urban smartness” as a key enabler.	Energy, information technology, construction	Unknown	Research program under preparation	5 - Responsible Leaders (3), Work Package Leader, Participant	Documentation of the research and innovation agenda

Fig. 2. Procedures used to analyze the empirical material.

a constructivist variant of grounded theory analysis (Charmaz, 2014) to ensure methodological congruence (for a similar approach, see Lauckner et al., 2012).

In analyzing the individual cases, we began with the research programs under preparation, which were “nested” in the case of knowledge ecosystems searching for their knowledge domain. In the first stage of analysis, data were open coded (Charmaz, 2014). Using NVivo software, we coded sentence-by-sentence and phrase-by-phrase, labelling passages from the empirical material to capture ideas or concepts. We tried to remain open to what the material suggested, utilizing “in-vivo” coding where applicable in order to stay as close to the data as possible. Along with grounded codes, theory codes were also introduced, similar to the *tabula geminus* approach elaborated by Kreiner (2016). The initial stage of data analysis for the larger research project sparked our interest in the organization of knowledge ecosystems and the literature on contemporary forms of organizing (e.g., Kellogg et al., 2006; Puranam et al., 2014). From that literature, we identified the concepts of meta-organization (e.g., Gulati et al., 2012), partial organization (e.g., Ahrne and Brunsson, 2011), and organizationality (Dobusch and Schoeneborn, 2015) as our sensitizing concepts (see Conceptual Background for further detail). These constructs were of initial interest to us and suggested “directions along which to look” (Blumer, 1954: 7).

While coding, we took an “interrogative” approach to the data in an effort to detect processes and actions, as well as elements of organization. Whenever the data allowed, we coded using gerunds (e.g., aligning, agreeing, communicating, etc.) in order to “gain a strong sense of action and sequence” (Charmaz, 2014: 120) that would speak to our research question of how knowledge ecosystems are organized. The initial codes varied in length from a couple of words to full sentences. We coded the interview transcripts independently, and we met regularly to discuss coding and resolve issues in order to arrive at a common set of codes. This process ensured that the coders interpreted the data in similar fashion and without missing any relevant information.

Through joint coding meetings, discussions, and multiple iterations of the data and our initial codes, we finally agreed a core set of codes with sufficient theoretical reach and relevance for our nascent analysis. We also reduced the number of open codes and began to think about “preliminary grouping” of codes. Hence, focused coding was initiated during the phase of open coding. Next, we analyzed the data from the ongoing research programs, “nested” in the case of knowledge ecosystems operating in their knowledge domain. The first author independently open-coded the interview transcripts, and the coding was discussed in a joint coding meeting with the second author. We are confident that theoretical saturation was reached, as analysis of the later set of interviews yielded no new theoretical insights.

Although focused coding began during open coding, joint coding meetings were dedicated to focused coding to select the most significant codes for theorizing. As the first and second author were responsible for coding, the third author participated in the analysis by playing the role

of “devil’s advocate,” providing a “new set of eyes” (Stake, 2000) to critically question and challenge the in-depth empirical knowledge of the other two. Detailed memos of our discussions were kept to ensure that all valuable and creative ideas about our analysis, and possible relationships between our codes, were recorded (e.g., Strauss and Corbin, 1998).

The combination of open and focused coding enabled us to conduct the within-case analysis, describing and analyzing what the cases were all about. From there, we returned to grounded theory analysis and focused coding to develop core categories in parallel with the cross-case analysis. By simultaneously a) making connections between the focused codes and b) comparing emergent core categories across the two cases, we differentiated two types of knowledge ecosystem: 1) those searching for a knowledge domain and 2) those searching within an identified knowledge domain. On further analysis, we found that these respectively corresponded to two forms of organizing: prefigurative and partial. In this final stage of analysis, we searched the literature for concepts and findings that would help to make sense of our initial findings. Applying the theoretical notion of partial organization, with its elements of membership and coordination (Ahrne and Brunsson, 2011; Gulati et al., 2012), served to refine the precision and clarity of our findings. In addition, we realized that two of our open codes, *formulating self-serving goals* and *sharing intermediate outputs*, could also be understood as *revealing*, where the first refers to “problem-related knowledge about needs they will face in current or future markets” and the second to “solution-related knowledge needed to develop technologies and products” (Alexy et al., 2013: 270). On that basis, we felt that the concept of *selective revealing* (Alexy et al., 2013) would best describe our findings. Finally, for presentation of the results, we employed the Gioia method (see Gioia et al., 2013). Fig. 3 illustrates our data structure, and Table 2 sets out research evidence in support of our open and focused coding.

The following sections detail our findings in relation to prefigurative and partial organizing in terms of two themes: joint search, and participation and coordination.

4. Knowledge ecosystem as prefigurative organization

4.1. Joint knowledge search

Before any joint research and innovation activities can begin, research program actors need to identify the “knowledge domain”—that is, the locus of joint knowledge search and creation activities and the problems to be addressed. We conceptualize this process as *searching for the knowledge domain*; that is, the search for the field of action where program-level knowledge creation and individual-level knowledge work will eventually take place. Specifically, the object of search is the overall universe of knowledge (or problem range), upon which a more focused search will happen later. This state provides distinct findings related to the organizing and organization, which we analyze here.

4.1.1. Formulating the common goal

The search for the knowledge domain is usually concretized as a common goal, which is explicitly outlined in the strategic research and innovation agenda drafted during preparation of the research program. Dialogue and discussion address how that common goal can be reached. According to our respondents, the common goal seems to serve two purposes. First, they explained that a common goal makes the research program more “convincing” and helps to “push” program participants following a positive funding decision. In that sense, the common goal can be understood as an antecedent of the actorhood pursued by the collective during execution of the research program. For example, one of our respondents from an ongoing program explained that a large research program enables them “to make statements as a bigger unit” and “to have more impact” on international standardization bodies. Second, the common goal was seen to help in differentiating the

Fig. 3. Data structure.

program from similar research activities and projects in the same knowledge domain, especially when applying for funding. However, in the words of one respondent, “composing this story of what we want (to) accomplish together” while specifying a distinctive goal “is not an easy task.”

It’s very difficult to find a common goal and target for this topic because it’s so broad. There’s also a lot of activity in relation to Smart Cities, so to find a target that distinguishes this program from all the other projects financed by Tekes or by EU funding is not an easy task. Where do we want Finnish companies and researchers to be after five to ten years, and why should we do [it]—why aren’t the ongoing projects enough to bring us there? (ReProG_Respondent E)

4.1.2. Probing

The search for a knowledge domain means identifying a unique and distinctive common goal. On the other hand, this requires those involved in the preparation of the research program to reveal their interests and intentions to some extent. While a research and innovation agenda’s distinctiveness can help to ensure partial funding from national or EU sources, the common goal must align at least in part with the private interests of the company partners if they are to invest financial resources in the program. In preparing a research program, participants often encounter a chicken-and-egg problem: should the research partners first define problems or opportunities that might prove to be of interest to companies, or should companies first indicate their needs, enabling the research partners to then provide solutions? Our respondents openly admitted being baffled by the question of “who is actually setting the targets.”

Our analysis suggests that probing can help in abstracting the common goal to a higher level. For example, one respondent indicated that when individuals “bring the company or university strategies in,” the revelation of strategic intent can become problematic in formulating a “radical and new” research and innovation agenda. It follows that it may be easier to envision a more radical and novel agenda for the research program by dispensing with their home organizations’ strategies.

When research program participants only partially disclose their intentions for joint research and innovation activities, “pieces of information” need to be collected. Collection of this scattered information

can take multiple forms, from listening to a company’s perspective on “what should be done, what should be researched” to one-on-one discussions to “map all ongoing activities that are going in the same direction.”

4.2. Participation and coordination

In identifying the field of the joint research and innovation activities, the coordination of that process rests on the shoulders of selected individuals, at best. In the preparation of a research program, coordination of the search for a knowledge domain remains informal, with no formal or determinate structures to help participants to coordinate identification of the program’s aims. The complexity of coordination is further increased because those involved in the preparation of emerging research programs are mere affiliates. For those reasons, we interpreted the organization of research programs under preparation as prefigurative.

4.2.1. Affiliation-based participation

Our analysis identifies *affiliation* as the basis of participation in research programs under preparation. By this we mean that the participants are closely involved in the preparation of the research program—for example, identifying the common goal and planning the program—but in identifying the field of the joint research and innovation, they are self-resourced and unobliged. We will distinguish later between affiliation and membership; in the latter, participation is based on regulation of membership and allocation of (collective) financial resources to members.

As there are no collective financial resources to cover the costs of participation while a research program is under preparation, each participant must be self-resourced. This means that individual participants must invest a lot of uncompensated time in the preparation, accepting the associated financial risks and postponing recruitment until the program secures funding.

A lot of costs are created; I think nobody understands how much. It takes a lot of our time. We are already calculating our hours in the preparation phase, so if you want to see afterwards how much time this has consumed, we can track it. That is of course the major cost, but it is not cheap either to organize these big events, with 100 people writing

Table 2
Representative empirical material reflecting open and focused codes.

Open and focused codes	Representative empirical material
1. Formulating the common goal	
A. Need to find a common goal	A1. And of course, this [program] is more convincing if we have a common goal. Let's find that. (ReProG_Respondent B) A2. We have noticed that the more focused the target is already at the beginning, the easier the preparation is. We want to find a solution through the program. (ReProG_Respondent B)
B. Dialogue and discussions	B1. We tried to get the consensus. And of course, that's typically not how it goes. Consensus does not mean that everyone agrees. There will be some participants who would like to see more of their own work included in the high-level topics. And in those cases, my way of handling this is to discuss with them. (ReProE_Respondent A) B2. The goal is to have a dialogue. Because many researchers have very good ideas, and companies are listening them. (ReProF_Respondent A)
2. Probing	
C. Who is actually setting the targets?	C1. Companies are maybe waiting for the suggestions from some research partners and then, on the other hand, research partners would like to focus the work based on the company needs. Which should come first and how to work from that? Now we've just been waiting for quite a long time for somebody to take a step forward. (ReProG_Respondent C) C2. We still don't know who should be the group to set the targets. We have noticed that the problem is that people cannot separate themselves from their roles in the company, in the university, when they are writing the agenda. They bring the strategy of the university or the company in and then [the research agenda] just flows from the obvious sources. It is not something radical and new. (ReProG_Respondent A)
D. Collecting 'pieces of information'	D1. Each partner needs to explain their own interest. We then combine the program out of those, not vice versa. (ReProE_Respondent A) D2. People like to look at the [research program] or whatever project is at hand in the vacuum solely. And they are not bringing up voluntarily all the connections they might know. I think that's one of the main challenge, then you don't get the big picture of what are all the instruments and activities going on in the same direction. (ReProG_Respondent D)
3. Affiliation	
E. Self-resourced participation	E1. It's a huge effort to do [the preparation]. If you are taking all those participants in the workshops into account, I think it was 150 people involved in the preparation. It went on for half a year. Of course, all of those were not involved all the time but I think it must be a huge sum of money that went into it, without producing any research. (ReProF_Respondent B) E2. I've learnt that the preparation is a lot of work. It's really time-consuming and requires a lot of connecting with people and creating networks and starting the discussions and trying to create these kinds of common goals and visions about what we should work with. It's sometimes a more difficult task than the research work that we then start. (ReProG_Respondent C)
F. Unobliged participation	F1. We cannot say yet who will be the partners. There are a lot of universities, a lot of research partners that want to join the project and few companies still. So, we'll see. (ReProF_Respondent C) F2. We still don't know who the final participants are because [the main funder] is making changes on the participant list all the time. They are dropping out some companies and changing their role et cetera. There's constant change in that. (ReProF_Respondent D)
4. Informal coordination	
G. Documenting the strategic research and innovation agenda (SRIA)	G1. There have been quite many larger workshops, or the whole day events, where the ideas of the core groups, the task group or the working group has been delivered and disseminated and then, discussed and getting feedback. (ReProG_Respondent D) G2. We have these writing sessions in May, early May. There, we will write the strategic research innovation agenda. And the persons that take part in this writing process, they have the power actually. (ReProF_Respondent C)
H. Absence of formal rules and decision making protocol	H1. There are no written rules nowadays, because the contract is not yet written and signed. (ReProF_Respondent F) H2. There is no formal decision making process because at that point, when you are preparing a research program, you don't have anything yet. You don't have the rules for collaboration; you don't have anything, so you can't have formal decision making structures because you don't have a program yet. (ReProF_Respondent D)
5. Reinforcing the common goal	
I. Aligning with, updating and broadening the common goal	I1. It's also important that we are talking about a four-year program, that we are not just looking at the original SRIA, but we should also update that. The world is changing so fast that even in four year programs you must change your direction in an agile manner if needed. (ReProD_Respondent C) I2. The programs need to be large enough. They need to have enough of critical mass. They need to have demanding, but flexible objectives. (ReProD_Respondent A)
J. Anchor events	J1. When the Sprint ends, we will have a review. In that review, we assess what we have done and what we have achieved. Is something left behind, something that we need to take off for the following Sprint. We also compare all those achievements and progress to the overall targets of the program. (ReProE_Respondent A) J2. You will see that as everyone else is contributing, you need to contribute as well and share the knowledge. (ReProD_Respondent A)
6. Selectively revealing	
K. Formulating self-serving goals	K1. If a company joins the program, it must have a fundamental purpose. It is not just joining the program. The participation should benefit the company's business and improve its profit in the long or mid-term. (ReProB_Respondent A) K2. In our program, every company defines their own goals. We call them business cases that outline the concrete targets for their participation. We expect every business case to involve at least one research partner, preferably several. (ReProD_Respondent A)
L. Sharing intermediate outputs	L1. We have a tool called JIRA where we collect records of all the outputs as they are produced. (ReProD_Respondent B) L2. The whole consortia meet every three months. It's kind of a mini-conference as such, so every three months almost 200 people come together. We have presentations, demo bazaars, planning sessions, business case planning, and a review of the results. (ReProD_Respondent C)
7. Membership	
M. Granting and regulating of membership	M1. New partners can join. And there are old partners leaving the program. We are happy to take in new partners and we discuss very openly if there are new partners willing to join. 10+ partners joined yesterday as we voted for their inclusion. (ReProB_Respondent A) M2. I've kept some partners outside of the program. I used the power of the academic coordinator to do that. (ReProB_Respondent B)

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Open and focused codes	Representative empirical material
N. Allocating (collective) financial resources to members	N1. Firm partners allocate resources to university partners. (ReProA_Respondent B) N2. We do [the allocation of the resources] in the steering group where the most important firm and university partners are represented. We don't allocate our financial resources based on micro-projects. (ReProD_Respondent B)
8. Formal regulation and monitoring	
O. Documents	O1. Documents that respondents brought up include the following: SRIA, program plan, budget, contract, and business cases.
P. Practices	P1. In the steering group meetings, we go through things that concern us all, and agree what happens next. (ReProD_Respondent A)

together—it will always cost several thousand to organize because you need a big space, and then some lunch, coffee, and things like that. (ReProG_Respondent E)

Only once preparation is completed and the application accepted can the research program receive funding from national (e.g., Tekes in Finland) or EU sources. In addition, for-profit companies may also provide financial resources.

In addition to being self-resourced, participation is also unobliged—that is participants have no obligation or commitment to the preparation or to the research program. Even when the program is ready to start, participants in the preparation can still decide to drop out if they so wish, or if a funder (e.g., Tekes) so chooses. Potential participants can be invited to workshops and meetings to hear about ongoing preparations and to articulate their ideas, but participation does not oblige them to become more involved.

Then the public call was made so that interested parties could declare their own interest in the program. (ReProE_Respondent A)

This open approach to participation on an affiliation-only basis naturally creates a flux in the composition of affiliates. By the time the program begins, the group of affiliates identifying the field of joint research and innovation activities may have changed in size or composition.

4.2.2. Informal coordination

Coordination of the group of affiliated participants is very informal in the preparation of the research program. As explained earlier, identifying the field of joint research activities relies on probing, dialogue, and discussions to assemble the “relevant pieces of information,” with no formal rules or decision-making protocols to support that process of identification.

One artefact that can help informal coordination is the strategic research and innovation agenda (SRIA), which documents the goal and vision of the research program—for example, the aim might be “to create the foundation for the success of the Finnish software intensive businesses in the new digital economy.” The SRIA enables participants to develop a form of “common knowledge” (Carlile, 2004), or what Bechky (2003) calls “common ground.”

5. Knowledge ecosystem as partial organization

5.1. Joint knowledge search

When the objective has been identified and joint research and innovation activities have begun, the knowledge ecosystem can be characterized as *searching within the knowledge domain*. This is quite distinct from the type of search process discussed above, as the overall scope of the knowledge domain within which solution search occurs is shared by all actors in the knowledge ecosystem. The collective and interactive nature of this search process means that this “landscape” is not static but constantly evolving. However, the shared understanding of the knowledge domain shapes search in a way that has clear implications for this process.

5.1.1. Reinforcing the common goal

While a common goal has been formulated in the preparation of a research program, that common goal needs to be reinforced when the knowledge ecosystem is exploring new knowledge in the identified knowledge domain. This means aligning with, updating, and/or broadening the common goal as needed—in other words, the knowledge domain is reconfigured and reframed. For example, new members can join the knowledge ecosystem, but their activities and interests must be aligned with the identified knowledge domain.

We're not limiting ourselves. If someone comes and says 'We have this really good idea,' it will basically be allowed if it fits our SRIA idea. So, that's the main thing—it needs to fit to the SRIA, and if that happens then all companies are welcome. (ReProA_Respondent A)

At the same time, the research program's common goal allows for flexibility, in that the goal can be updated or broadened. When a research program is being prepared, the goal is formulated with a four-year time frame in mind. However, if “the world is going somewhere else” than at the time of preparation, the goal or the direction can be changed in agile fashion.

Anchoring events such as the two-day review meetings provide an arena for reflecting on and reinforcing the common goal. Every third month, program participants gather to discuss both what has been achieved and what has been neglected in relation to the common goal. We found that the two-day review meetings resembled Garud et al.'s (2014) description of anchor events as “venues for creation, maintenance, and rejuvenation of networks that constitute ecosystems” (p. 1183), providing “occasions for temporal coordination, and retrospective, real-time, and prospective sensemaking” (p. 1184).

5.1.2. Selectively revealing

When research program participants conduct research and innovation activities within the identified knowledge domain, they reveal proprietary information in two ways. First, they formulate self-serving goals—for example, in one of the research programs, each participating organization defined their own goals on a yearly basis in the form of a business case. Such a goal explicates the fundamental reason for a participant's desire to get involved in the program. For company participants in particular, the purpose cannot simply be to participate; rather, participation must benefit their business by generating more revenue, for example, or improving their profits. The second way of revealing proprietary information is to share intermediate outputs; these may include academic conference and journal publications, prototypes, and software. In the research programs, all intermediate outputs are available to all participants.

5.2. Participation and coordination

As research activities in the identified field conclude, coordination becomes more formal. Participation becomes membership-based, with inherent obligations, and members can now use collective resources to support their participation. Formal organizing elements monitor the progress of joint research activities and improve the visibility of members' contributions. For these reasons, and reflecting our findings against the concept of partial organization (Ahrne and Brunsson, 2011),

we interpret the organization of these research programs as partial in nature.

5.2.1. Membership-based participation

Even after work has commenced within the identified knowledge domain, research programs still welcome new participants; in other words, the boundaries of these knowledge ecosystems remain open both for newcomer entry and for the departure of current members. Nevertheless, membership is regulated, and although there is, as our respondents noted, “an open dialog about new members,” program steering groups ultimately vote on the admission of new members. In some cases, it may be the responsibility of steering group members to keep aspiring members away.

Members are entitled to a share of the collective financial resources. We noted that allocation of these resources can happen in one of two ways, depending on the program in question. First, company members can allocate financial resources directly to a particular research partner, so selecting who they will collaborate with and initiating or securing membership for that research participant. Where direct investment in a company member is the prevailing resourcing practice, research partners lobby companies or steering group members in the hope of securing resources for membership. Alternatively, the steering group can take full responsibility for allocation of financial resources to avoid program fragmentation, as one respondent involved in such a program explained.

This [resource allocation practice] creates real collaboration instead of competing against one another [for resources]. Competition [for resources] would kill us all. I don't believe that we can grow into an ecosystem if [resource allocation] is fragmented. (ReProD_Respondent B)

5.2.2. Formal regulation and monitoring

Once participants become official members, their participation is no longer a matter of unobligated affiliation. They are now entitled to a share of the collective financial resources, and their contributions are monitored. To monitor the progress of the planned research and the contributions of individual members, research programs utilize documents such as the SRIA, as well as the program plan, budget, key performance indicators, and reports.

6. Discussion and conclusion

For the purposes of this study, we have adopted an organizational perspective to explain joint knowledge search and creation in knowledge ecosystems. Key findings and theoretical contributions are summarized in Fig. 4. Based on our findings from the collective case study, we have differentiated two types of knowledge ecosystem: those searching *for* a knowledge domain and those searching *within* a knowledge domain. To identify a knowledge domain or operate within it, the knowledge ecosystem engages in *joint knowledge search*, which refers to the actual substance of knowledge creation, both in identifying a valuable problem landscape and in searching within a specified landscape (cf. Nickerson and Zenger, 2004). This difference in nature and target of joint search has implications for how knowledge ecosystems are organized, the associated challenges, their degree of organizational ability, and the related absence or presence of organizing elements (cf. Ahrne and Brunsson, 2011).

In this study, we also established that the organization of knowledge ecosystems differs on two dimensions: participation and coordination (see Fig. 4). *Participation* relates to the role and relationship of individual actors to the collective and how and to what extent they contribute to the broader organizational entity (see Puranam et al., 2014). Based on our findings, we propose that in the prefigurative form of organizing, participation is affiliation-based. Ecosystem-affiliated actors provide self-resourced inputs to the knowledge ecosystem, such as contributions to probing the knowledge domain. In the partial form,

where joint knowledge search occurs within a knowledge domain, participation is membership-based. Actors can access collective resources, are monitored for their contributions, and are bound to the knowledge ecosystem by their membership.

Coordination refers to integration of the inputs and efforts of the individual actors that comprise the organization (see for example March and Simon, 1993; Puranam et al., 2014). Based on our findings, we propose that in the prefigurative form of organizing, coordination to integrate inputs and efforts—in our case, dispersed viewpoints and initiatives—is informal. Here, the inputs and efforts of affiliated participants are gathered to formulate a common goal; in so doing, they assist the process of identifying the knowledge domain. In the partial form, coordination is based on formal monitoring and regulation with reference to preset criteria and plans. Here, knowledge search occurs within the identified knowledge domain, and members collectively participate in solution-oriented knowledge creation activities.

We also identified main *organizing challenges* for the two forms of knowledge ecosystems. In general, the existence of a clear overarching goal and a sense of direction allows the ecosystem members to bond, enables collaboration and shapes the ecosystem-level focus (see also Moore, 1996; Iansiti and Levien, 2004). For the prefigurative form, we found that there is a lot of ambiguity over the direction of joint knowledge search and the eventual domain of activities. This relates to diverse expectations about e.g. who should be setting the goals, and it can make the joint search for a knowledge domain quite challenging. Indeed, in early-stage ecosystems the challenge often is that actors wait for each other to take initiative and set direction (see e.g. Pellinen et al., 2012; Dattée et al., 2018). For the partial form of organizing, every member's unique agenda and goals can lead to a different set of challenges. For instance, some companies have their own specific goals for developing new kinds of products or services, and as there can be a lot of variety among the individual goals, it can lead to actors working quite separately. Thus, it is vital for the collective to find an appropriate balance between members' own goals and the common goal to which they can relate, and through which they can accomplish their agenda (see e.g. Nambisan and Baron, 2013).

To summarize: knowledge ecosystems are organized to perform joint knowledge search, and the nature of this search has implications for a feasible organizing form and degree of organizational ability. Overall, these findings are supported in the light of previous literature where the nature of the search has been suggested to have implications for effectiveness of organizing choices (see for example Felin and Zenger, 2014; Lopez-Vega et al., 2016). The following sections discuss the specific implications of our findings for theory, policy, and practice, the study's limitations, and future research opportunities.

6.1. Implications for theory

We contribute to the nascent literature of *knowledge ecosystems* by providing an empirically grounded theorizing of their organization, examining knowledge ecosystems where collective search either seeks to identify a knowledge domain or is conducted within a jointly shared domain. On that basis, we propose a refined, empirically grounded definition of the knowledge ecosystem: *A knowledge ecosystem consists of users and producers of knowledge, organized around joint knowledge search.*

Theoretically, our study contributes to three ongoing discussions. First, in relation to the literature on *knowledge search*, our findings illuminate knowledge ecosystems as a particular way of organizing problem identification and search. This complements earlier studies that identified various governance modes and search paths for knowledge exploration in closed and open innovation contexts (Felin and Zenger, 2014; Lopez-Vega et al., 2016). In particular, our results show how knowledge ecosystems organize around two forms of problem search (Nickerson and Zenger, 2004): identification of a problem domain and searching within a jointly agreed problem domain. In this regard, we found differences between prefigurative and partial

Fig. 4. Forms of organizing in knowledge ecosystems.

organization forms of knowledge ecosystems. The former involves tentative probing, identifying a jointly interesting knowledge domain in attempting to satisfy diverse knowledge search motivations within the tentative overall goals of the ecosystem. The latter type combines selective revealing of knowledge search goals by individual actors (see Alexy et al., 2013) with reframing and renegotiation of the solution domain. While the two types of knowledge ecosystem were found to correspond to different frames of knowledge search, we also found that the process entails significant ambiguity and movement back and forth between the two types of search. It seems likely, then, that different knowledge ecosystems (i.e. those beyond our empirical context) involve different configurations of search processes. As recently suggested by von Hippel and von Krogh (2015), problem-solution pairs are not always found through a linear process of identification; instead, the process may be asymmetric and complex. Our results suggest that when solving the problem, reframing may occur, creating an iterative linkage back to problem identification. Given the complexity of knowledge ecosystems, collective processes of problem identification and problem solving are therefore likely to be parallel and intertwined in many cases.

Second, the present study contributes to the literature on *innovation and knowledge ecosystems* by clarifying the coordination and participation of the actors constituting a knowledge ecosystem. In this regard, we diverge from the previous ecosystem literature, which has often addressed the single focal actor's coordination efforts (Rohrbeck et al., 2009; Leten et al., 2013; Ritala et al., 2013) or the structural aspects of

knowledge and innovation ecosystems (Still et al., 2014; Clarysse et al., 2014). The present approach allows us to examine the important organizational features of knowledge ecosystems: interdependence between the actors and collective efforts toward knowledge integration. In the existing literature, interdependence among ecosystem actors has been examined mainly from a technological perspective, as in the interdependence between platform owner and complementors (see for example Wareham et al., 2014) or from the customer perspective, where an ecosystem is needed to create value for a complex customer need or challenging value proposition (see for example Williamson and De Meyer, 2012). Here, we touch on interdependence (or the lack of it) in organizing knowledge integration. It has been suggested that the knowledge work of each individual actor is interdependent with the knowledge work of others—even multiple others—and that interdependencies may constrain and reduce the menu of feasible research and development projects (Ethiraj and Posen, 2013). Previous research has also shown that new knowledge creation is enhanced by crossing knowledge boundaries and domains of expertise (Bruno, 2013; Perry et al., 2016), and our results provide evidence of how knowledge ecosystems organize this crucial knowledge integration task, showing the extent of actors' involvement in knowledge creation, what motivates them, and the rights and responsibilities involved.

Third, we contribute to the *organizational* literature, with particular regard to non-traditional forms of organization such as the meta-organization (Gulati et al., 2012) or “actor-oriented architectural schemes” (Fjeldstad et al., 2012). In its focus on joint search, the knowledge

ecosystem can be understood as a particular type of meta-organization. This conceptualization corresponds to the call to understand organizations more comprehensively than just as individual firms (Ahrne and Brunsson, 2011). Here, our study demonstrates how meta-organizations such as knowledge ecosystems are organized via prefigurative and partial forms, which adds detail to Ahrne and Brunsson's (2011) dichotomy of partial and formal/complete organizations. Relatedly, our findings highlight the relevance of the concept of organizationality (Dobusch and Schoeneborn, 2015) in a knowledge creation context. For the prefigurative form of knowledge ecosystem, identification of a common goal provided a basis for actorhood, and formal organizing elements were anticipated and expected rather than merely absent. These aspects allowed for a certain level of organizationality even in very early stage knowledge ecosystems.

Finally, as the focus is clearly on knowledge creation, organizing knowledge ecosystems involves a partially different set of activities and challenges than those encountered by meta-organizations centered on manufacturing or logistics, for example. In the prefigurative form, participants have to navigate through the ambiguity in setting the direction for joint knowledge search, which can be linked to the absence of clear expectations, formal organizing elements (cf. Ahrne and Brunsson, 2011) as well as the fact that membership status is in flux (Dobusch and Schoeneborn, 2015). Prior research (see Järvenpää and Välikangas, 2014, 2016) has shown that the ambiguity experienced in such early stage exploratory collaborations has implications for participants sharing behavior since long-term benefits or losses of knowledge sharing are not yet visible. Such organizing challenges are pronounced in prefigurative form –knowledge ecosystems, where the basis for knowledge sharing and creation is still emerging. For the partial form, the challenges are more related to balancing of private and common goals, which is already closer to the setting encountered also in more formally organized collaborative networks and systems (e.g. Lavie, 2006). In fact, prior literature has argued that in such structures, the heterogeneity of participants can make the coordination of independent tasks, and dealing with opportunistic behaviors rather challenging (Provan et al., 2007). According to Gulati et al. (2012), clear communication and decision-making channels can allow a certain degree of transparency to individual members' activities and decisions, and therefore provide a base for coordination. Our study shows that partial form –knowledge ecosystems indeed involve some organizing elements helping in such coordination, while the absence of “complete organization²” still upholds the challenge of balancing private and common goals.

6.2. Implications for policy and practice

Many policy initiatives such as those in the present empirical setting are advanced and funded by national governments, innovation agencies, and supra-national research funding bodies (see for example Levén et al., 2014; Sinnewe et al., 2016). Knowledge and innovation ecosystems are often promoted as vehicles for regional and national development, as well as for new innovations to address large-scale societal problems or boost national growth. As significant resources are typically allocated to implementing such policy initiatives, it is important to understand the critical factors for successful execution.

Based on our findings, we offer the following practical recommendations for executing policy initiatives that promote problem-solving within knowledge ecosystems. First, it is important to understand the type of knowledge ecosystem in play and to choose the appropriate means of supporting its development. In the case of

² “Complete” or “formal” organizations have access to all elements of organizing (cf. Ahrne and Brunsson, 2011). In our empirical setting none of the studied knowledge ecosystems had evolved into “complete” organizations. However, we acknowledge that some knowledge ecosystems – beyond the current study – could bear a more close resemblance to a “complete organization”.

knowledge ecosystems searching for a knowledge domain, instruments that link a diverse range of actors or that enable actors to participate in the formulation of a common goal should be prioritized over pure R&D funding instruments, as they are likely to have a bigger impact in facilitating goal-setting. On the other hand, when the knowledge ecosystem is searching within a shared knowledge domain, R&D funding instruments can accelerate the development of solutions, and it is up to policymakers (perhaps in an interactive process with ecosystem actors) to determine which domains are worthy of support.

Secondly, as a related issue, our findings suggest that managers and policy makers should ensure the development of capabilities for knowledge and innovation ecosystem governance. As shown by Sinnewe et al. (2016), it can be challenging to sustain collaboration between industry and academic institutions once funding ends. Given the role of knowledge ecosystems in addressing large-scale problems, it seems important to sustain collaboration between actors in the absence of public funding. In this regard, ecosystem management capabilities, including resourcing and governance mechanisms that enable knowledge creation activities to be coordinated cost-effectively, can help to sustain collaboration within the ecosystem.

6.3. Limitations and future research directions

Like any exploratory qualitative research, this study has some inherent limitations related to context-specificity and generalizability. First, our empirical setting involves the central role of for-profit firms as leading actors in knowledge ecosystems. Therefore, our research context might not fully correspond to knowledge ecosystems where research institutions in a particular geographical context would have a dominant role, for instance. Thus, future research could address different types of knowledge ecosystems and provide comparative analyses. Nevertheless, we believe that our findings provide a useful overview of how knowledge ecosystems are organized.

One key limitation relates to the lack of observational data that might have provided a better understanding of events (such as anchoring events) where key organizing decisions were made. As access to these events was negotiated but not granted, we had to rely on participants' accounts. In addition, the present study addressed only the early stages of collective knowledge development and did not include other collective activities such as commercialization. Future research might usefully address the organizational aspects of these processes, which are often covered in the literature on innovation networks and ecosystems. In addition, future research could enrich the present framework by investigating possible outcomes or outputs of knowledge ecosystems (e.g., financial outcomes, knowledge creation, business ecosystems, and successful execution of policy initiatives). Finally, future research can build on our findings by adopting a process perspective to understand the evolution of knowledge ecosystems and their organization—for example, the transition from prefigurative to partial organization, or more detailed temporal examination of change in the organizing elements of knowledge and innovation ecosystems.

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References

- Ahrne, G., Brunsson, N., 2005. Organizations and meta-organizations. *Scand. J. Manage.* 21, 429–449.
- Ahrne, G., Brunsson, N., 2011. Organization outside organizations: the significance of partial organization. *Organization* 18, 83–104.
- Alexy, O., George, G., Salter, A.J., 2013. Cui bono? The selective revealing of knowledge and its implications for innovative activity. *Acad. Manage. Rev.* 38, 270–291.
- Autio, E., Thomas, L.D.W., 2014. Innovation ecosystems: implications for innovation management. In: Dodgson, M., Gann, D.M., Phillips, N. (Eds.), *Oxford Handbook of Innovation Management*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, pp. 204–228.
- Barley, W.C., 2015. Anticipatory work: how the need to represent knowledge across boundaries shapes work practices within them. *Organ. Sci.* 26, 1612–1628.
- Barry, D., Rerup, C., 2006. Going mobile: aesthetic design considerations from Calder and the constructivists. *Organ. Sci.* 17, 262–276.
- Baxter, P., Jack, S., 2008. Qualitative case study methodology: study design and implementation for novice researchers. *Qual. Rep.* 13, 544–559.
- Bechky, B.A., 2003. Sharing meaning across occupational communities: the transformation of understanding on a production floor. *Organ. Sci.* 14, 312–330.
- Beyer, J.M., Hannah, D.R., 2002. Building on the past: enacting established personal identities in a new work setting. *Organ. Sci.* 13, 636–652.
- Blumer, H., 1954. What is wrong with social theory? *Am. Sociol. Rev.* 18, 3–10.
- Bogers, M., Ollila, S., Yström, A., 2016. Designing and being designed: organizing complex collaborative innovation in a societal challenge. Best Paper Proceedings of the 76th Academy of Management Annual Meeting.
- Bruns, H.C., 2013. Working alone together: coordination in collaboration across domains of expertise. *Acad. Manage. J.* 56, 62–83.
- Carlile, P.R., 2002. A pragmatic view of knowledge and boundaries: boundary objects in new product development. *Organ. Sci.* 13, 442–455.
- Carlile, P.R., 2004. Transferring, translating, and transforming: an integrative framework for managing knowledge across boundaries. *Organ. Sci.* 15, 555–568.
- Charmaz, K., 2014. *Constructing Grounded Theory*. SAGE Publications Ltd., London, UK.
- Clarisse, B., Wright, M., Bruneel, J., Mahajan, A., 2014. Creating value in ecosystems: crossing the chasm between knowledge and business ecosystems. *Res. Policy* 43, 1164–1176.
- Corsaro, D., Cantù, C., Tunisini, A., 2012. Actors' heterogeneity in innovation networks. *Ind. Market. Manage.* 41, 780–789.
- Dahllander, L., Gann, D.M., 2010. How open is innovation? *Res. Policy* 39, 699–709.
- Dattée, B., Alexy, O., Autio, E., 2018. Maneuvering in poor visibility: how firms play the ecosystem game when uncertainty is high. *Acad. Manage. J.* 61 (2), 466–498. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5465/amj.2015.0869>.
- Davis, J.P., 2016. The group dynamics of interorganizational relationships: collaborating with multiple partners in innovation ecosystems. *Admin. Sci. Q.* 61 (4), 621–661. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0001839216649350>.
- Davis, J.P., Eisenhardt, K.M., 2011. Rotating leadership and collaborative innovation: recombination processes in symbiotic relationships. *Admin. Sci. Q.* 56, 159–201.
- Dobusch, L., Schoeneborn, D., 2015. Fluidity, identity, and organizational: the communicative constitution of Anonymus. *J. Manage. Stud.* 52 (8), 1005–1035.
- Dougherty, D., Dunne, D.D., 2011. Organizing ecologies of complex innovation. *Organ. Sci.* 22, 1214–1233.
- Eisenhardt, K.M., 1989. Building theories from case study research. *Acad. Manage. Rev.* 14, 532–550.
- Ethiraj, S., Posen, H.E., 2013. Do product architectures affect innovation productivity in complex product ecosystems? *Adv. Strateg. Manage.* 30, 127–166.
- Felin, T., Zenger, T.R., 2014. Closed or open innovation? Problem solving and the governance choice. *Res. Policy* 43, 914–925.
- Fjeldstad, Ø.D., Snow, C.C., Miles, R.E., Lettl, C., 2012. The architecture of collaboration. *Strateg. Manage. J.* 33, 734–750.
- Franzoni, C., Sauerhahn, H., 2014. Crowd science: the organization of scientific research in open collaborative projects. *Res. Policy* 43, 1–20.
- Garud, R., Gehman, J., Giuliani, A.P., 2014. Contextualizing entrepreneurial innovation: a narrative perspective. *Res. Policy* 43, 1177–1188.
- Garud, R., Jain, S., Tuertscher, P., 2008. Incomplete by design and designing for incompleteness. *Organ. Stud.* 29, 351–371.
- Gavetti, G., Levinthal, D., 2000. Looking forward and looking backward: cognitive and experiential search. *Admin. Sci. Q.* 45, 113–137.
- Gawer, A., 2014. Bridging different perspectives on technological platforms: toward and integrative framework. *Res. Policy* 43, 1239–1249.
- Gioia, D.A., Corley, K.G., Hamilton, A.L., 2013. Seeking qualitative rigor in inductive research notes on the Gioia methodology. *Organ. Res. Methods* 16, 15–31.
- Gulati, R., Puranam, P., Tushman, M., 2012. Meta-organization design: rethinking design in interorganizational and community contexts. *Strateg. Manage. J.* 33, 571–586.
- Halme, K., Lindy, I., Piirainen, K.A., Salminen, V., White, J., 2014. *Finland as a Knowledge Economy 2.0: Lessons on Policies and Governance*. World Bank Publications.
- Iansiti, M., Levien, R., 2004. Strategy as ecology. *Harv. Bus. Rev.* (March), 69–78.
- Järvenpää, S., Välikangas, L., 2014. Opportunity creation in innovation networks. *Calif. Manage. Rev.* 57, 67–87.
- Järvenpää, S., Välikangas, L., 2016. From governance void to interactive governing behaviors in new research networks. *Acad. Manage. Discov.* 2, 226–246.
- Kellogg, K.C., Orlikowski, W.J., Yates, J., 2006. Life in the trading zone: structuring coordination across boundaries in post-bureaucratic organizations. *Organ. Sci.* 17, 22–44.
- King, B.G., Felin, T., Whetten, D.A., 2010. Perspective - finding the organization in organizational theory: a meta-theory of the organization as a social actor. *Organ. Sci.* 21, 290–305.
- Kreiner, G.E., 2016. *Tabula geminus - a "both/and" approach to coding and theorizing*. In: Elsbach, K.D., Kramer, R.M. (Eds.), *Handbook of Qualitative Organizational Research*. Routledge, New York, NY.
- Lauckner, H., Paterson, M., Krupa, T., 2012. Using constructivist case study methodology to understand community development processes: proposed methodological questions to guide the research process. *Qual. Rep.* 17 (13), 1–22.
- Lavie, D., 2006. The competitive advantage of interconnected firms: an extension of the resource-based view. *Acad. Manage. Rev.* 31 (3), 638–658.
- Leten, B., Vanhaverbeke, W., Roijakkers, N., Clerix, A., Van Helleputte, J., 2013. IP models to orchestrate innovation ecosystems. *Calif. Manage. Rev.* 55 (4), 51–64.
- Levén, P., Holmström, J., Mathiassen, L., 2014. Managing research and innovation networks: evidence from a government sponsored cross-industry program. *Res. Policy* 43 (1), 156–168.
- Lindkvist, L., 2005. Knowledge communities and knowledge collectivities: a typology of knowledge work in groups. *J. Manage. Stud.* 42, 1189–1210.
- Lopez-Vega, H., Tell, F., Vanhaverbeke, W., 2016. Where and how to search? Search paths in open innovation. *Res. Policy* 45, 125–136.
- Macher, J.T., 2006. Technological development and the boundaries of the firm: a knowledge-based examination in semiconductor manufacturing. *Manage. Sci.* 52, 826–843.
- March, J.G., Simon, H.A., 1993. *Organizations revisited*. *Ind. Corp. Change* 2, 299–316.
- Moore, J.F., 1996. *The Death of Competition: Leadership and Strategy in the Age of Business Ecosystems*. Harper Business, New York.
- Nambisan, S., Baron, R.A., 2013. Entrepreneurship in innovation ecosystems: entrepreneurs' self-regulatory processes and their implications for new venture success. *Entrepreneur. Theory Pract* 37, 1071–1097.
- Nickerson, J.A., Zenger, T.R., 2004. A knowledge-based theory of the firm—The problem-solving perspective. *Organ. Sci.* 15, 617–632.
- Ostrom, E., 1990. *Governing the Commons: The Evolution of Institutions for Collective Action*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK.
- Parlett, M., Hamilton, D., 1972. *Evaluation as Illumination: A New Approach to the Study of Innovative Programs*. Occasional Paper. Centre for Research in the Educational Sciences, University of Edinburgh, Edinburgh.
- Pellinen, A., Ritala, P., Järvi, K., Sainio, L.M., 2012. Taking initiative in market creation—a business ecosystem actor perspective. *Int. J. Bus. Environ.* 5, 140–158.
- Perkmann, M., Schildt, H., 2015. Open data partnerships between firms and universities: the role of boundary organizations. *Res. Policy* 44, 1133–1143.
- Perry, S.J., Hunter, E.M., Currall, S.C., 2016. Managing the innovators: organizational and professional commitment among scientists and engineers. *Res. Policy* 45, 1247–1262.
- Powell, W.W., Koput, K.W., Smith-Doerr, L., 1996. Interorganizational collaboration and the locus of innovation: networks of learning in biotechnology. *Admin. Sci. Q.* 41, 116–145.
- Provan, K.G., Fish, A., Sydow, J., 2007. Interorganizational networks at the network level: a review of the empirical literature on whole networks. *J. Manage.* 33, 479–516.
- Puranam, P., Alexy, O., Reitzig, M., 2014. What's "new" about new forms of organizing? *Acad. Manage. Rev.* 39, 162–180.
- Ritala, P., Agouridas, V., Assimakopoulos, D., Gies, O., 2013. Value creation and capture mechanisms in innovation ecosystems: a comparative case study. *Int. J. Technol. Manage.* 63, 244–267.
- Rohrbeck, R., Hölzle, K., Gemünden, H.G., 2009. Opening up for competitive advantage – How Deutsche Telekom creates an open innovation ecosystem. *R&D Manage.* 39, 420–430.
- Rosenkopf, L., Metiu, A., George, V.P., 2001. From the bottom up? Technical committee activity and alliance formation. *Admin. Sci. Q.* 46, 748–772.
- Sammarra, A., Biggiero, L., 2008. Heterogeneity and specificity of Inter-Firm knowledge flows in innovation networks. *J. Manage. Stud.* 45, 800–829.
- Schreyögg, G., Sydow, J., 2010. Crossroads - organizing for fluidity? Dilemmas of new organizational forms. *Organ. Sci.* 21, 1251–1262.
- Scott, W.R., Davis, G.F., 2007. *Organizations and Organizing: Rational, Natural and Open Systems Perspectives*. Routledge.
- Seawright, J., Gerring, J., 2008. Case selection techniques in case study research - a menu of qualitative and quantitative options. *Polit. Res. Q.* 61, 294–308.
- Sinkovics, R.R., Alfoldi, E.A., 2012. Progressive focusing and trustworthiness in qualitative research - the enabling role of computer-assisted qualitative data analysis software (CAQDAS). *Manage. Int. Rev.* 52, 817–845.
- Sinnewe, E., Charles, M.B., Keast, R., 2016. Australia's Cooperative Research Centre Program: a transaction cost theory perspective. *Res. Policy* 45, 195–204.
- Snow, C.C., Fjeldstad, Ø.D., Lettl, C., Miles, R.E., 2011. Organizing continuous product development and commercialization: the collaborative community of firms model. *J. Prod. Innov. Manage.* 28, 3–16.
- Stake, R.E., 1981. The art of progressive focusing. In: *Proceedings of the 65th Annual Meeting of the American Educational Research Association*. Los Angeles.
- Stake, R.E., 1995. *The Art of Case Study Research*. Sage Publications, Inc., Thousand Oaks, CA.
- Stake, R.E., 2000. Case studies. In: Denzin, N.K., Lincoln, Y.S. (Eds.), *Handbook of Qualitative Research*. Sage Publications, Inc., Thousand Oaks, CA, pp. 435–454.
- Still, K., Huhtamäki, J., Russell, M.G., Rubens, N., 2014. Insights for orchestrating innovation ecosystems: the case of EIT ICT labs and data-driven network visualisations. *Int. J. Technol. Manage.* 66, 243–265.
- Strauss, A., Corbin, J., 1998. *Basics of Qualitative Research: Techniques and Procedures for Developing Grounded Theory*. Sage Publications, Inc, Thousand Oaks, CA.
- Sydow, J., Windeler, A., Schubert, C., Möllering, G., 2012. Organizing R&D consortia for path creation and extension: the case of semiconductor manufacturing technologies. *Organ. Stud.* 33, 907–936.

- Teles, 2016. Strategic Centres for Science, Technology and Innovation (SHOK). <http://www.tekes.fi/en/programmes-and-services/strategic-centres/>.
- Valkokari, K., 2015. Business, innovation, and knowledge ecosystems: how they differ and how to survive and thrive within them. *Technol. Innov. Manage. Rev.* 5 (8), 17–24.
- Wareham, J., Fox, P.B., Cano Giner, J.L., 2014. Technology ecosystem governance. *Organ. Sci.* 25, 1195–1215.
- West, J., Salter, A., Vanhaverbeke, W., Chesbrough, H., 2014. Open innovation: the next decade. *Res. Policy* 43, 805–811.
- van der Borgh, M., Cloudt, M., Romme, A.G.L., 2012. Value creation by knowledge-based ecosystems: evidence from a field study. *R&D Manage.* 42, 150–169.
- von Hippel, E., Von Krogh, G., 2015. CROSSROADS—Identifying viable “Need–Solution Pairs”: problem solving without problem formulation. *Organ. Sci.* 27, 207–221.
- Wilhoit, E.D., Kisselburgh, L.G., 2015. Collective action without organization: the material constitution of bike commuters as collective. *Organ. Stud.* 36, 573–592.
- Williamson, P., De Meyer, A., 2012. Ecosystem advantage: how to successfully harness the power of partners. *Calif. Manage. Rev.* 55, 24–46.
- Yazan, B., 2015. Three approaches to case study methods in education: Yin, Merriam, and Stake. *Qual. Rep.* 20, 134–152.